

Market Brief: Emerging and Disruptive Technologies for CEI

Emerging and disruptive technologies are crucial enablers of future Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) solutions. These technologies are in various stages of development and have the potential to significantly reshape CEI applications, driving future innovation and capabilities in the CEI landscape.

Key Technologies:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Generative AI (GenAI):

- ✔ **Status and Maturity:** AI investment in Europe surged to EUR 46.4 billion in 2024, with software accounting for 57.0%, services 23.7%, and hardware 19.3%. AI adoption is driven by operational efficiency needs and competitive pressure. Generative AI is expected to account for one-third of the AI market by 2028.
- ✔ **Expected Developments:** AI spending is forecast to grow to EUR 133.6 billion by 2028. Improvements in model accuracy, efficiency, and explainability are anticipated, driven by innovations in algorithms, data processing, and hardware.
- ✔ **Importance for CEI:** AI enhances CEI solutions in energy, mobility, and manufacturing by enabling dynamic scenarios for grid optimization, adaptive transportation networks, automation and predictive maintenance strategies.

5G Advanced and 6G:

- ✔ **Status and Maturity:** The 3GPP continues to issue new releases for 5G and 5G Advanced, with key improvements like Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communications (URLLC), network slicing, and non-terrestrial networks (NTNs). 6G development is expected to begin around 2029.
- ✔ **Expected Developments:** 5G Advanced releases will provide further improvements in AI/ML integration, advanced positioning, and energy efficiency. 6G will focus on terahertz frequencies, AI-native network design, and integrated sensing and communication.
- ✔ **Importance for CEI:** Advanced connectivity will support the growing processing demands of IoT and AI, enabling real-time applications and enhancing Europe's industrial capabilities.

Swarm Intelligence:

- ✔ **Status and Maturity:** Swarm intelligence involves systems of autonomous agents coordinating actions through decentralized control. Core algorithms are well-established, but implementation is still evolving.
- ✔ **Expected Developments:** Swarm technology will integrate AI/ML for enhanced decision-making, develop heterogeneous swarms, and expand to new sectors like healthcare and urban planning.
- ✔ **Importance for CEI:** Swarm technology aligns with the decentralized nature of CEI, enabling robust and resilient systems for disaster response, infrastructure monitoring, and smart city management.

Satellite Connectivity:

- ✔ **Status and Maturity:** Satellite communications are evolving with reusable launch technology and low-earth orbit (LEO) satellite fleets, increasing capacity and reducing costs.
- ✔ **Expected Developments:** Satellite connectivity will expand to more IoT use cases, with lower costs and integration with terrestrial networks.
- ✔ **Importance for CEI:** Satellite connectivity addresses coverage gaps in remote areas, enabling consistent and reliable connectivity for CEI deployments in agriculture, energy, and transportation.

Intelligent Energy:

- ✔ **Status and Maturity:** CEI solutions demand significant energy, especially for AI model training. Companies are prioritizing power consumption and seeking zero-carbon energy for GenAI workloads.
- ✔ **Expected Developments:** Trends include hardware and algorithm optimization, AI-powered energy management, edge computing deployment, and power capping implementation.
- ✔ **Importance for CEI:** Energy efficiency and sustainability are crucial for CEI development, requiring comprehensive monitoring and optimization across the CEI continuum.

Advances in Cybersecurity:

- ✔ **Status and Maturity:** AI is central to cybersecurity, enabling threat detection and automated responses. Quantum computing is in early stages, with efforts under way to develop quantum-resistant encryption.
- ✔ **Expected Developments:** AI-driven security platforms will expand, and quantum-resistant algorithms will be developed. Breakthroughs in quantum computing will drive shifts in encryption practices.
- ✔ **Importance for CEI:** Integrated security measures are essential for protecting CEI solutions across cloud, edge, and IoT environments, ensuring cyber-resilience and secure digital operations.

